

Root ideotype for water stress environments

Problem

Water excess (waterlogging) and deficit (drought) can severely limit crop growth and productivity. As the global climate changes, instances of extreme rainfall or periods of no rainfall are increasing. This will have an impact on global and local crop productivity. Crops access water via their root systems. The resilience of crops to drought and waterlogging conditions is impacted by how well they are rooted in the soil and by the architectural, anatomical and biochemical makeup of their root systems.

Solution

Root traits with evidence for improving resilience to waterlogging and/or drought were developed into root ideotypes (a model of an ideal root system), with priority root traits indicated where more evidence was available. Ideotypes have been developed for cereal, faba bean and potato crop species, considering the four different environmental scenarios of waterlogging, early drought, late drought and water stress (a combinations of these).

Benefits

Through breeding and managing these crop species to exhibit these ideal root traits, water capture will be improved, enhancing crop yield in water stress prone environments and improving crop resilience to a changing climate and weather extremes.

Practical recommendations

There are two types of water stress, water excess (**waterlogging**) and water deficit (**drought**). The key elements to improve a crops ability to withstand these environmental stresses are different and outlined below.

Waterlogging:

- More **aerenchyma** – these are straw like structures which can develop in root systems to increase air flow within the root tissue while the roots are in saturated soil. Acting a bit like a snorkel to allow air flow.
- Greater **adventitious root porosity**, again forming more air spaces in the adventitious (or nodal) roots.

Drought:

- **Deeper** roots with **greater root density** at depth to access water deeper in the soil profile.
- **Greater root hair density**, which increases surface area to increase water uptake.
- Increased **early root vigour** which is more specific to early water deficit (pre-flowering).

Other lower priority and related traits include greater root dry weight, more aerenchyma and greater root porosity. These traits reduce the carbon cost of root construction and allow the plants to invest more in root length, and associate with more mycorrhiza and rhizobia, which can increase water uptake.

Applicability box

Theme: Root traits to improve crop water stress resilience

Keywords: Ideotype, water, drought, waterlogging, root length density, root hairs, aerenchyma

Context: Regions and soils prone to waterlogging and/or drought

Period of impact: Medium to long term, dependent on finding genetic markers for identified traits that can be transferred into modern varieties

Best in: Plant breeding; all soils and regions prone to drought or waterlogging

Figure 1: Example root ideotypes for water stress environments. The highlighted traits for each environment are the same for each species included and the full set of example ideotypes can be found in deliverable 1.2.

Further information

- Root2Res Deliverable 1.2 Define target ideotypes. <https://zenodo.org/records/19564381>
- Root2Res Practice Abstract: Root ideotype for a low phosphorus environment. <https://zenodo.org/records/19564425>
- Root2Res Podcast Episode: Exploring Root Ideotypes and Plasticity: Strategies for Resilient Agriculture. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VImB0sq8Ds>
- Lynch, J.P. (2013) Steep, cheap and deep: an ideotype to optimize water and N acquisition by maize root systems. *Annals of Botany*. 112, 347–357. doi: [10.1093/aob/mcs293](https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcs293).
- Schmidt, J.E. and Gaudin, A.C.M. (2017). Toward an Integrated Root Ideotype for Irrigated Systems. *Trends in Plant Science*. Vol. 22, No. 5, 433-443. doi: [10.1016/j.tplants.2017.02.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2017.02.001).
- Berry, P.M., Sylvester-Bradley, R. and Berry, S. (2007). Ideotype design for lodging-proof wheat. *Euphytica*. 154, 165-179. doi: [10.1007/s10681-006-9284-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-006-9284-3)

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

Publisher: ADAS

Authors: Charlotte White, Christina Baxter, Ben Hague, Pete Berry (all ADAS)

Contact: christina.baxter@adas.co.uk & charlotte.white@adas.co.uk

Review: Nina Gallmann, Laura Kemper (both FiBL)

Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/records/19564449>

This practice abstract was elaborated in the Root2Resilience project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format.

© 2026

Root2Resilience: The project is running from September 2022 to August 2027. The overall goal of Root2Resilience – Root phenotyping and genetic improvement for rotational crops resilient to environmental change – is to develop root phenotyping, genetic and modelling tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils

Project website: root2res.eu

Funding

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra
Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Root2Resilience has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101060124. Its work is supported by Innovate UK through the Horizon Europe Guarantee scheme Grant Agreement No. 101060124 and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under grant No. 23.00050.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), European Research Executive Agency (REA) or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor any other granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The authors and editors do not assume responsibility or liability for any possible factual inaccuracies or damage resulting from the application of the recommendations in this practice abstract.